

dl-*Tricycloekasantalic acid* was prepared in an analogous way. Crystallisation in this case was comparatively difficult and the yield was even poorer; m.p. 75°: Equiv. wt. 194.2. (Found: C, 73.99; H, 9.60. $C_{12}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 74.19; H, 9.33 per cent). Methyl ester, b. p. 127°/10 mm; n_D^{20} , 1.4783 (Found: C, 74.3; H, 10.1. $C_{13}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 74.3; H, 10.5 per cent).

Further work for the preparation of optically pure *tricycloekasantalic acid* by a different method is in progress.

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORIES,
INDIAN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE,
BANGALORE.

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STUDIES IN THE SANTALOL SERIES. PART III. SYNTHESES OF *d*- α -SANTALAL AND *d*- α -SANTALOL

BY P. C. GUHA AND S. C. BHATTACHARYYA

The aldehyde *tricycloekasantal* has been condensed with propionic aldehyde in presence of alcoholic alkali to produce *d*-santalal. Santalal has been reduced with aluminium ethoxide to *d*- α -santalol, identical with the natural product.

In Part II of this series, the syntheses of some of the degradation products of *d*- α -santalol has been dealt with. In this part, the syntheses of the parent substance *d*- α -santalol, as also of the corresponding aldehyde *d*- α -santalal has been described. Semmier made a very exhaustive study of the chemistry of the degradation products of α -santalol and ascribed to it ($C_{15}H_{24}O$) the structure (I).

According to him, α -santalol (I) is a tricyclic primary alcohol with a long side-chain possessing an ethylenic linkage. When *d*- α -santalol (I) is oxidised with chromic

acid in acetic acid solution (Semmler, *Ber.*, 1907, 40, 1120, 1124) it forms the aldehyde *n*- α -santalal, $C_{15}H_{22}O$ (II). With dilute permanganate solution α -santalol (I) produces α -santalol glycol (III) which is subsequently oxidised to hydroxyacetone (IV) and tricycloekasantalic acid (V) (Semmler, *loc. cit.*, Simonsen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 309).

Structure of tricycloekasantalic acid was known from the work of Semmler (*Ber.*, 1910, 43, 445, 1723, 1893) and has been definitely established from our synthesis described in Part II of this series. Therefore, α -santalol must have the structure (I), consequently α -santalal must be represented by (II).

Tautomerism.—Recently Simonsen (*loc. cit.*) has made the important observation that α -santalol (I) exists in a tautomeric form (VI).

Simonsen, besides isolating tricycloekasantalic acid, tricycloekasantalal (VIII) (Semmler, *Ber.*, 1907, 40, 1120) and hydroxyacetone (IV) from the products of ozonolysis of α -santalol (I), has also established the presence of formaldehyde by preparing its characteristic methone derivative. Moreover, by the ozonolysis of α -santalyl chloride he could isolate, though in an impure form, a chloroketone (VII) and formaldehyde. The results can only be interpreted on the assumption that α -santalol (I) can exist in a second tautomeric form (VI).

Here is a peculiar difficulty in interpreting oxidation experiments where the groups

are involved, since products corresponding to both the forms are obtained. These phenomena, though they appear rather peculiar, are not quite uncommon among the terpenes.

Kuhn and Roth (*Ber.*, 1932, 65, 1255) quantitatively estimated the amount of acetone formed during the oxidation of similar compounds (e.g. dehydrogeranic acid) by ozone followed by potassium permanganate. They found that in general the quantity of acetone amounts to 60-90% of the theory, the quantity being still less with potassium permanganate-oxidation. This type of linkage is considered to be mobile either under the influence of reagents or in solution, and may be interpreted as due to tautomerism. According to Simonsen, santalol is endowed with this kind of tautomeric properties.

Some Stereochemical Considerations.—No mention seems to have been made by the earlier workers of the possibility of α -santalol molecule existing in three geometrically isomeric forms shown below :

On oxidation of α -santalol with ozone and permanganate, *tricycloekasantalic acid* (V) and the corresponding aldehyde *tricycloekasantalal* (VIII) are obtained as the main products. Consequently, it may be reasonably assumed that the major bulk of natural α -santalol consists of compound (I). Moreover, in the isolated variety of natural α -santalol, which had to undergo a long course of heating during isolation by repeated fractional distillation, it is probable that only the more stable variety of the forms (A) and (B) will predominate.

In Part II of this series, the synthesis of *tricycloekasantalic acid* (V) has been described. In the experiments described in the present paper the corresponding aldehyde, *tricycloekasantalal* (VIII) has been utilised as the starting material for building up the α -santalol molecule. Semmler (*loc. cit.*) has shown that the methyl ester of *tricycloekasantalic acid* gives the corresponding alcohol, *tricycloekasantalol* (IX) on reduction; the latter can be converted by oxidation into the corresponding aldehyde, *tricycloekasantalal* (VIII).

The same aldehyde can be obtained by the direct ozonolysis of natural α -santalol. The latter process of the ozonolysis of natural α -santalol has now been utilised for the preparation of this aldehyde. Because the synthesis of tricycloekasantalic acid has now been achieved, that of the aldehyde follows automatically. It is therefore immaterial whichever process is utilised for the preparation of this aldehyde.

Tricycloekasantalal (VIII) undergoes aldol condensation with propionic aldehyde in presence of dilute alcoholic alkali producing the unsaturated aldehyde, α -santalal (II), identical with the product obtained from natural α -santalol by oxidation.

The aldol (X), formed at the intermediate stage, could not be isolated. The yield used to vary due to the simultaneous self-condensation of propionic aldehyde, the maximum yield obtained was however 20%. α -Santalal (II), thus obtained, has been reduced with aluminium alcoholate to the alcohol, α -santalol (I), identical with the natural product. To elucidate the tautomeric character of synthetic α -santalol it was subjected to the process of ozonisation in the products of which no formaldehyde could be detected. As the amount of substance at our disposal was very limited, the inference of the ozonisation experiment cannot be regarded as confirmed. Further experiments on the direct synthesis of the tautomeric variety (C) are in progress.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Tricycloekasantalal.—Pure natural α -santalol (20 g.) was ozonised in ethyl acetate solution. After the ozonisation was complete, the solvent was removed by distillation under reduced pressure and the ozonide of α -santalol decomposed by heating with water and shaken thoroughly with potassium bicarbonate solution to remove any tricycloekasantalic acid formed. The insoluble oily layer after extraction with ether was distilled in vacuum. The aldehyde was then purified through its bisulphite compound in the usual way and finally redistilled. Yield was variable 3–3.5 g. could be obtained; b.p. 110°/111°/10 mm; n_D^{20} , 1.4852; n_D^{25} , 1.4845; n_D^{30} , 1.4845; n_D^{35} , 1.4845; n_D^{40} , 1.4845; n_D^{45} , 1.4845; n_D^{50} , 1.4845; n_D^{55} , 1.4845; n_D^{60} , 1.4845; n_D^{65} , 1.4845; n_D^{70} , 1.4845; n_D^{75} , 1.4845; n_D^{80} , 1.4845; n_D^{85} , 1.4845; n_D^{90} , 1.4845; n_D^{95} , 1.4845; n_D^{100} , 1.4845; n_D^{105} , 1.4845; n_D^{110} , 1.4845; n_D^{115} , 1.4845; n_D^{120} , 1.4845; n_D^{125} , 1.4845; n_D^{130} , 1.4845; n_D^{135} , 1.4845; n_D^{140} , 1.4845; n_D^{145} , 1.4845; n_D^{150} , 1.4845; n_D^{155} , 1.4845; n_D^{160} , 1.4845; n_D^{165} , 1.4845; n_D^{170} , 1.4845; n_D^{175} , 1.4845; n_D^{180} , 1.4845; n_D^{185} , 1.4845; n_D^{190} , 1.4845; n_D^{195} , 1.4845; n_D^{200} , 1.4845; n_D^{205} , 1.4845; n_D^{210} , 1.4845; n_D^{215} , 1.4845; n_D^{220} , 1.4845; n_D^{225} , 1.4845; n_D^{230} , 1.4845; n_D^{235} , 1.4845; n_D^{240} , 1.4845; n_D^{245} , 1.4845; n_D^{250} , 1.4845; n_D^{255} , 1.4845; n_D^{260} , 1.4845; n_D^{265} , 1.4845; n_D^{270} , 1.4845; n_D^{275} , 1.4845; n_D^{280} , 1.4845; n_D^{285} , 1.4845; n_D^{290} , 1.4845; n_D^{295} , 1.4845; n_D^{300} , 1.4845; n_D^{305} , 1.4845; n_D^{310} , 1.4845; n_D^{315} , 1.4845; n_D^{320} , 1.4845; n_D^{325} , 1.4845; n_D^{330} , 1.4845; n_D^{335} , 1.4845; n_D^{340} , 1.4845; n_D^{345} , 1.4845; n_D^{350} , 1.4845; n_D^{355} , 1.4845; n_D^{360} , 1.4845; n_D^{365} , 1.4845; n_D^{370} , 1.4845; n_D^{375} , 1.4845; n_D^{380} , 1.4845; n_D^{385} , 1.4845; n_D^{390} , 1.4845; n_D^{395} , 1.4845; n_D^{400} , 1.4845; n_D^{405} , 1.4845; n_D^{410} , 1.4845; n_D^{415} , 1.4845; n_D^{420} , 1.4845; n_D^{425} , 1.4845; n_D^{430} , 1.4845; n_D^{435} , 1.4845; n_D^{440} , 1.4845; n_D^{445} , 1.4845; n_D^{450} , 1.4845; n_D^{455} , 1.4845; n_D^{460} , 1.4845; n_D^{465} , 1.4845; n_D^{470} , 1.4845; n_D^{475} , 1.4845; n_D^{480} , 1.4845; n_D^{485} , 1.4845; n_D^{490} , 1.4845; n_D^{495} , 1.4845; n_D^{500} , 1.4845; n_D^{505} , 1.4845; n_D^{510} , 1.4845; n_D^{515} , 1.4845; n_D^{520} , 1.4845; n_D^{525} , 1.4845; n_D^{530} , 1.4845; n_D^{535} , 1.4845; n_D^{540} , 1.4845; n_D^{545} , 1.4845; n_D^{550} , 1.4845; n_D^{555} , 1.4845; n_D^{560} , 1.4845; n_D^{565} , 1.4845; n_D^{570} , 1.4845; n_D^{575} , 1.4845; n_D^{580} , 1.4845; n_D^{585} , 1.4845; n_D^{590} , 1.4845; n_D^{595} , 1.4845; n_D^{600} , 1.4845; n_D^{605} , 1.4845; n_D^{610} , 1.4845; n_D^{615} , 1.4845; n_D^{620} , 1.4845; n_D^{625} , 1.4845; n_D^{630} , 1.4845; n_D^{635} , 1.4845; n_D^{640} , 1.4845; n_D^{645} , 1.4845; n_D^{650} , 1.4845; n_D^{655} , 1.4845; n_D^{660} , 1.4845; n_D^{665} , 1.4845; n_D^{670} , 1.4845; n_D^{675} , 1.4845; n_D^{680} , 1.4845; n_D^{685} , 1.4845; n_D^{690} , 1.4845; n_D^{695} , 1.4845; n_D^{700} , 1.4845; n_D^{705} , 1.4845; n_D^{710} , 1.4845; n_D^{715} , 1.4845; n_D^{720} , 1.4845; n_D^{725} , 1.4845; n_D^{730} , 1.4845; n_D^{735} , 1.4845; n_D^{740} , 1.4845; n_D^{745} , 1.4845; n_D^{750} , 1.4845; n_D^{755} , 1.4845; n_D^{760} , 1.4845; n_D^{765} , 1.4845; n_D^{770} , 1.4845; n_D^{775} , 1.4845; n_D^{780} , 1.4845; n_D^{785} , 1.4845; n_D^{790} , 1.4845; n_D^{795} , 1.4845; n_D^{800} , 1.4845; n_D^{805} , 1.4845; n_D^{810} , 1.4845; n_D^{815} , 1.4845; n_D^{820} , 1.4845; n_D^{825} , 1.4845; n_D^{830} , 1.4845; n_D^{835} , 1.4845; n_D^{840} , 1.4845; n_D^{845} , 1.4845; n_D^{850} , 1.4845; n_D^{855} , 1.4845; n_D^{860} , 1.4845; n_D^{865} , 1.4845; n_D^{870} , 1.4845; n_D^{875} , 1.4845; n_D^{880} , 1.4845; n_D^{885} , 1.4845; n_D^{890} , 1.4845; n_D^{895} , 1.4845; n_D^{900} , 1.4845; n_D^{905} , 1.4845; n_D^{910} , 1.4845; n_D^{915} , 1.4845; n_D^{920} , 1.4845; n_D^{925} , 1.4845; n_D^{930} , 1.4845; n_D^{935} , 1.4845; n_D^{940} , 1.4845; n_D^{945} , 1.4845; n_D^{950} , 1.4845; n_D^{955} , 1.4845; n_D^{960} , 1.4845; n_D^{965} , 1.4845; n_D^{970} , 1.4845; n_D^{975} , 1.4845; n_D^{980} , 1.4845; n_D^{985} , 1.4845; n_D^{990} , 1.4845; n_D^{995} , 1.4845; n_D^{1000} , 1.4845; n_D^{1005} , 1.4845; n_D^{1010} , 1.4845; n_D^{1015} , 1.4845; n_D^{1020} , 1.4845; n_D^{1025} , 1.4845; n_D^{1030} , 1.4845; n_D^{1035} , 1.4845; n_D^{1040} , 1.4845; n_D^{1045} , 1.4845; n_D^{1050} , 1.4845; n_D^{1055} , 1.4845; n_D^{1060} , 1.4845; n_D^{1065} , 1.4845; n_D^{1070} , 1.4845; n_D^{1075} , 1.4845; n_D^{1080} , 1.4845; n_D^{1085} , 1.4845; n_D^{1090} , 1.4845; n_D^{1095} , 1.4845; n_D^{1100} , 1.4845; n_D^{1105} , 1.4845; n_D^{1110} , 1.4845; n_D^{1115} , 1.4845; n_D^{1120} , 1.4845; n_D^{1125} , 1.4845; n_D^{1130} , 1.4845; n_D^{1135} , 1.4845; n_D^{1140} , 1.4845; n_D^{1145} , 1.4845; n_D^{1150} , 1.4845; n_D^{1155} , 1.4845; n_D^{1160} , 1.4845; n_D^{1165} , 1.4845; n_D^{1170} , 1.4845; n_D^{1175} , 1.4845; n_D^{1180} , 1.4845; n_D^{1185} , 1.4845; n_D^{1190} , 1.4845; n_D^{1195} , 1.4845; n_D^{1200} , 1.4845; n_D^{1205} , 1.4845; n_D^{1210} , 1.4845; n_D^{1215} , 1.4845; n_D^{1220} , 1.4845; n_D^{1225} , 1.4845; n_D^{1230} , 1.4845; n_D^{1235} , 1.4845; n_D^{1240} , 1.4845; n_D^{1245} , 1.4845; 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n_D^{1970} , 1.4845; n_D^{1975} , 1.4845; n_D^{1980} , 1.4845; n_D^{1985} , 1.4845; n_D^{1990} , 1.4845; n_D^{1995} , 1.4845; n_D^{2000} , 1.4845; n_D^{2005} , 1.4845; n_D^{2010} , 1.4845; n_D^{2015} , 1.4845; n_D^{2020} , 1.4845; n_D^{2025} , 1.4845; n_D^{2030} , 1.4845; n_D^{2035} , 1.4845; n_D^{2040} , 1.4845; n_D^{2045} , 1.4845; n_D^{2050} , 1.4845; n_D^{2055} , 1.4845; n_D^{2060} , 1.4845; n_D^{2065} , 1.4845; n_D^{2070} , 1.4845; n_D^{2075} , 1.4845; n_D^{2080} , 1.4845; n_D^{2085} , 1.4845; n_D^{2090} , 1.4845; n_D^{2095} , 1.4845; n_D^{2100} , 1.4845; n_D^{2105} , 1.4845; n_D^{2110} , 1.4845; n_D^{2115} , 1.4845; n_D^{2120} , 1.4845; n_D^{2125} , 1.4845; n_D^{2130} , 1.4845; n_D^{2135} , 1.4845; n_D^{2140} , 1.4845; n_D^{2145} , 1.4845; n_D^{2150} , 1.4845; n_D^{2155} , 1.4845; n_D^{2160} , 1.4845; n_D^{2165} , 1.4845; n_D^{2170} , 1.4845; n_D^{2175} , 1.4845; n_D^{2180} , 1.4845; n_D^{2185} , 1.4845; n_D^{2190} , 1.4845; n_D^{2195} , 1.4845; n_D^{2200} , 1.4845; n_D^{2205} , 1.4845; n_D^{2210} , 1.4845; n_D^{2215} , 1.4845; n_D^{2220} , 1.4845; n_D^{2225} , 1.4845; n_D^{2230} , 1.4845; n_D^{2235} , 1.4845; n_D^{2240} , 1.4845; n_D^{2245} , 1.4845; n_D^{2250} , 1.4845; n_D^{2255} , 1.4845; n_D^{2260} , 1.4845; n_D^{2265} , 1.4845; n_D^{2270} , 1.4845; n_D^{2275} , 1.4845; n_D^{2280} , 1.4845; n_D^{2285} , 1.4845; n_D^{2290} , 1.4845; n_D^{2295} , 1.4845; n_D^{2300} , 1.4845; n_D^{2305} , 1.4845; n_D^{2310} , 1.4845; n_D^{2315} , 1.4845; n_D^{2320} , 1.4845; n_D^{2325} , 1.4845; n_D^{2330} , 1.4845; n_D^{2335} , 1.4845; n_D^{2340} , 1.4845; n_D^{2345} , 1.4845; n_D^{2350} , 1.4845; n_D^{2355} , 1.4845; n_D^{2360} , 1.4845; n_D^{2365} , 1.4845; n_D^{2370} , 1.4845; n_D^{2375} , 1.4845; n_D^{2380} , 1.4845; n_D^{2385} , 1.4845; n_D^{2390} , 1.4845; n_D^{2395} , 1.4845; n_D^{2400} , 1.4845; n_D^{2405} , 1.4845; n_D^{2410} , 1.4845; n_D^{2415} , 1.4845; n_D^{2420} , 1.4845; n_D^{2425} , 1.4845; n_D^{2430} , 1.4845; n_D^{2435} , 1.4845; n_D^{2440} , 1.4845; n_D^{2445} , 1.4845; n_D^{2450} , 1.4845; n_D^{2455} , 1.4845; n_D^{2460} , 1.4845; n_D^{2465} , 1.4845; n_D^{2470} , 1.4845; n_D^{2475} , 1.4845; n_D^{2480} , 1.4845; n_D^{2485} , 1.4845; n_D^{2490} , 1.4845; n_D^{2495} , 1.4845; n_D^{2500} , 1.4845; n_D^{2505} , 1.4845; n_D^{2510} , 1.4845; n_D^{2515} , 1.4845; n_D^{2520} , 1.4845; n_D^{2525} , 1.4845; n_D^{2530} , 1.4845; n_D^{2535} , 1.4845; n_D^{2540} , 1.4845; n_D^{2545} , 1.4845; n_D^{2550} , 1.4845; n_D^{2555} , 1.4845; n_D^{2560} , 1.4845; n_D^{2565} , 1.4845; n_D^{2570} , 1.4845; n_D^{2575} , 1.4845; n_D^{2580} , 1.4845; n_D^{2585} , 1.4845; n_D^{2590} , 1.4845; n_D^{2595} , 1.4845; n_D^{2600} , 1.4845; n_D^{2605} , 1.4845; n_D^{2610} , 1.4845; n_D^{2615} , 1.4845; n_D^{2620} , 1.4845; n_D^{2625} , 1.4845; n_D^{2630} , 1.4845; n_D^{2635} , 1.4845; n_D^{2640} , 1.4845; n_D^{2645} , 1.4845; n_D^{2650} , 1.4845; n_D^{2655} , 1.4845; n_D^{2660} , 1.4845; n_D^{2665} , 1.4845; n_D^{2670} , 1.4845; n_D^{2675} , 1.4845; n_D^{2680} , 1.4845; n_D^{2685} , 1.4845; n_D^{2690} , 1.4845; n_D^{2695} , 1.4845; n_D^{2700} , 1.4845; n_D^{2705} , 1.4845; n_D^{2710} , 1.4845; n_D^{2715} , 1.4845; n_D^{2720} , 1.4845; n_D^{2725} , 1.4845; n_D^{2730} , 1.4845; n_D^{2735} , 1.4845; n_D^{2740} , 1.4845; n_D^{2745} , 1.4845; n_D^{2750} , 1.4845; n_D^{2755} , 1.4845; n_D^{2760} , 1.4845; n_D^{2765} , 1.4845; n_D^{2770} , 1.4845; n_D^{2775} , 1.4845; n_D^{2780} , 1.4845; n_D^{2785} , 1.4845; n_D^{2790} , 1.4845; n_D^{2795} , 1.4845; n_D^{2800} , 1.4845; n_D^{2805} , 1.4845; n_D^{2810} , 1.4845; n_D^{2815} , 1.4845; n_D^{2820} , 1.4845; n_D^{2825} , 1.4845; n_D^{2830} , 1.4845; n_D^{2835} , 1.4845; n_D^{2840} , 1.4845; n_D^{2845} , 1.4845; n_D^{2850} , 1.4845; n_D^{2855} , 1.4845; n_D^{2860} , 1.4845; n_D^{2865} , 1.4845; n_D^{2870} , 1.4845; n_D^{2875} , 1.4845; n_D^{2880} , 1.4845; n_D^{2885} , 1.4845; n_D^{2890} , 1.4845; n_D^{2895} , 1.4845; n_D^{2900} , 1.4845; n_D^{2905} , 1.4845; n_D^{2910} , 1.4845; n_D^{2915} , 1.4845; n_D^{292

small amount of a second fraction, b.p. 100°/5 mm. which was nothing but *tricyclo-ekasantalal*. The third fraction, b.p. 138-145°/5 mm., was α -santalal. A higher boiling residue remained in the flask. The third fraction was redistilled; δ -santalal distilled at 143°/5 mm. It was finally purified through its semicarbazone. Pure aldehyde was prepared from the semicarbazone by decomposing the latter with phthalic anhydride and distilling in steam according to the method of Semmler (*loc. cit.*), yield 2.2 g. (approx); b.p. 143°/5 mm.: 153°/10 mm.: n_D^{20} , 1.5104; n_D , +14.1°; d_4^{20} , 0.9951. (Found: C, 82.78; H, 10.81. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{22}O$: C, 82.5; H, 10.1 per cent.). (As it is an α - β -unsaturated aldehyde, it is liable to undergo Cannizzaro's reaction and traces of a substance appearing like α -santalallic acid (*vide* part IV) could be detected in the residue left in the flask.)

The *semicarbazone* was prepared in the usual way from santalal (1 g.), semicarbazide hydrochloride (1.2 g.), sodium acetate (1.5 g.) in alcoholic solution. The precipitate was recrystallised from alcohol; m.p. 219-20° (corrected). Sample of santalal-semicarbazone, prepared from natural α -santalol, melts at 220°. (Found: C, 69.5; H, 9.36; N, 15.57. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{25}ON_3$: C, 69.81; H, 9.1; N, 15.3 per cent.).

d- α -Santalol.—Santalal (3 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (25 c.c.) containing aluminium ethylate (2 g.) and allowed to stand at room temperature for 4 days and then slowly refluxed on the water-bath for 5 hours. Alcohol was distilled off and the residue was heated with 10% potassium hydroxide (50 c.c.) for 15 minutes and extracted with ether and distilled in vacuum. α -Santalal distilled at 143°/5 mm.; b. p. 158°/10 mm., 148°/5 mm., 143.44°/3 mm.; n_D^{25} , 1.5013; d_{25}^{25} , 0.9970; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ 66.4; Calc. $C_{15}H_{24}$ $\sqrt{I} = 65.93$; $\alpha_{5730} = +9.6^\circ$; $\alpha_{5460} = +11.1^\circ$; unsaturation value 1.00; strychnine salt of hydrogen phthalate, m.p. 145° (Found: C, 81.52; H, 10.58. $C_{15}H_{24}O$ requires C, 81.8; H, 10.9 per cent.).